

Christianity and Lai Customary Law: Changes and Continuity

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ABSTRACT: This paper examines the cultural evolution and transformations experienced by the Lai tribe, primarily settled in the Lawngtlai district in southern Mizoram. Economically underdeveloped and the least urbanized in the state, Lawngtlai has a literacy rate of 66.41%, the lowest in Mizoram. Prior to the introduction of Christianity, the Lais had a distinct culture, along with well-established customary laws and practices. Village governance was traditionally led by the chiefs and their Upas (village elders). However, with the advent of British rule and the influence of Welsh Christian missionaries, the Lai culture underwent significant changes. Over time, much of the traditional culture has become "Christianized." This paper aims to explore the Lai's traditional cultural practices, the shifts in their customs—particularly in marriage, divorce, language, and traditional dances—as well as changes in village administration. It will also analyze both the positive and negative impacts of these cultural transformations.

Keywords: Customary Law, Lai, Lawngtlai, Mizoram, LIKBK, British Christian Missionary.

INTRODUCTION

Change is a fundamental aspect of all human societies, whether primitive or modern. No society can remain static or avoid the natural laws of change. This reality has long been a central focus for sociologists studying the evolving dynamics of human life and social relationships. The nature and complexity of social change have sparked numerous questions among social thinkers, such as: "Is change desirable?" "Is it necessary?" or "Has development come at the expense of preserving cultural heritage?" In other words, change does not always yield positive outcomes, and it may not always result in sustainable development. For social researchers, the challenge lies in studying these shifts to address these thought-provoking questions.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This paper aims to highlight the customary laws and practices of the Lai tribe, as well as the changes they have undergone, particularly in areas such as marriage and divorce customs, language, traditional dances, and ancient village administration. It explores both the positive and negative transformations within Lai culture. Given the limited literature on the Lai and their unique cultural heritage, this paper seeks to shed light on these distinct aspects of Lai life. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of incorporating Lai cultural elements into all current and future development programs to ensure balanced and sustainable growth within the Lai community. By doing so, this paper hopes to address the gap in the study of developmental programs, which have often overlooked cultural considerations, both in academic research and government initiatives, particularly in the context of Mizoram.

METHODOLOGY: Since, the paper deals with the traditional way of life of the Lais, the paper is thus qualitative in its approach. It employs both primary and secondary data. The primary source of data collection includes in-depth interview and telephonic interview with prominent personnels and the secondary sources of data are mainly collected from books, memoirs, journals, thesis and souvenirs as well.

THE LAI PEOPLE

The Lai indigenous community is primarily located in Mizoram's southernmost district, Lawngtlai, which shares international borders with Myanmar to the east and Bangladesh to the west. Lawngtlai was designated as a district on September 18, 1998, and is known for having one of the highest concentrations of minority populations in India, particularly in its western region. Economically, it is one of the most underdeveloped districts in Mizoram. According to the 2011 census, the population of Lawngtlai District was 117,894. The Lais are known by different names in various regions, such as 'Pawi' in Mizoram and Manipur, 'Chin' in Myanmar, and 'Shendus' in Bangladesh (Doungel, 2014: 220). Due to their socio-economic backwardness, the Lais were granted an Autonomous District Council, known as the Lai Autonomous District Council (LADC), on April 29, 1972, under the Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution. The Lais are part of the Mongoloid group of Burmese descent, having migrated and settled in the southeastern part of Mizoram (Vanlalringa, 2012: 7). They are believed to have originated from southern China and share the same ethnic roots as the Lusei (Mizo) and other Zo-ethnic tribes. The Lais were among the first Mizo tribes to migrate from China, initially settling in the Hukong Valley of Myanmar around 400 A.D. (Lehman, 1980: 18). From there, they moved further south to the Chindwin Valley (Laitanga, 1998: 8). According to prominent local historian Hengmanga, the Lai settlements in Myanmar's Chin Hills occurred between 1300 and 1700 A.D. (Hengmanga, 1980: 12). In the late 18th century, some of the Lai people began to migrate towards their current location in Mizoram (Vanlalringa, 2012: 8).

THE TRADITIONAL LAI CULTURE AND PRACTICES

The Lai cultural practices and way of life will be best reflected through their marriage and divorce practices, a glimpse of their language and their traditional dances and finally the Lai ancient village administration will also be mentioned so as to highlight an insight on the Lai's way of life and their social organisation.

MARRIAGE

The common form of marriage among the Lai is monogamy. However, polygamy was also practised by the chiefs and the noble men in the olden days. Although a man is allowed to have more than one wife, the only children of one of his wives called 'Nutak' shall enjoy inheritance right. To decide his best wife, a husband has to go through ceremonial ritual called 'Arnak' with her, so that she shall become his first or best wife and their children shall enjoy the inheritance right. The other wives are called 'Nuchhun' and their children shall have no right to claim for their father's properties (The Pawi- Lakher Autonomous Region Inheritance of Property Act, 1959; Vanlalringa, 2012:28). The most common form of marriage was 'Taitipur' wherein a mutual agreement from both the bride and bridegroom will be sought and are usually settled through 'Palai'(mediator). 'Lawipi' is another type of marriage where the wife directly followed the mediator to the bridegroom's house. This was practised mainly because of financial issues where the bridegroom did not have enough money for the bride-price.

‘Umhnawh’(matrilocal) was also practised but quite rare where the husband resides in a bride’s house. ‘Rawlti’ (elopement) was also the common practice even in the ancient times. Marriage was an expensive affair among the Lai and the bride-price differed among the various sub-tribes.

DIVORCE

The Lai customary Law do not restrict any person from divorcing on proper and sufficient ground. ‘Inmak’ is the most common form of divorce where the husband clears all the marriage price and the wife can take back her ‘thilchhawm’(dowry). ‘Sumchhuah’ is a divorce when the the wife was eager to divorce the husband so much so that she returns all the bride-price whereas ‘sumlaitan’ is a divorce of mutual understanding and marriage price was equally distributed between the husband and wife. When a wife commits adultery, she is called ‘uire’ and she has to return all the bride-price and their children will be kept by the husband only. If a wife becomes mentally abnormal, a husband has to bear with her for at least three years and in case she does not recover within that stipulated time, the husband may divorce her through ‘Peksachang’ meaning he loses all the marriage price. In another case, when a husband is abnormal and the wife divorces him before three years, it is regarded as ‘sumchhuah’ meaning that the wife has to give back the bride-price. The Lai customary Law also permits that the wife may initiates a divorce due to impotency of the husband for at least six months known as ‘nukaitheilo’ and ‘chhuping’ is a type of divorce when a wife cannot sleep with the husband for more than six months (Vanlalringa,2012 :42).

The British had encroached upon the land of the Lai since 1872 (Chinzah, 2003:26-27) and the subsequent arrival of the Christian Missionaries in the year 1903-1907 had tremendously changed the Lai customary laws and practices pertaining to marriage and divorce. Christian way of wedding ceremony held in the church has nowadays been prevalent over the traditional form of Lai marriage practice. The Lai dress and traditional attires have partly lost their usages and the western dress code is popularly used nowadays. The bride-price which was comparatively high in the olden days has now become more reasonable. However, comparing to the other tribes in Mizoram, the Lai bride-price is still slightly higher and it has never been cheaper than ₹ 5000. (Telephonic Interviewed with H.C.Lalnuthara on 6th May, 2022). Moreover, the bride-price still differs from tribe to tribe. The practice of polygamy by the affluent people in the past has no longer been found in today’s society. This, perhaps, may be regarded as the positive influence of Christian Teachings (Telephonic Interview with H.C. Lalnunhara on 6th May,2022). On the other hand, divorce rate is said to be comparatively higher as against the olden days. A research conducted in Lawnglai district by Ngurthanpuii and Dr.Jaisee Geetha have revealed that elopement has become the common form of marriage and higher chances of divorce are detected by marriage through elopement, early age marriage and in joint family (Ngurthanpuii and Geetha, 2017:1086). Due to introduction of modern system of education by the Christian Missionaries, individual rights and freedom has been strongly asserted by the educated people so much so that the institutions marriage and divorce have been taken much lightly as compared to the olden days.

LANGUAGE

The current Lai language spoken within the area of Lai Autonomous District Council, Lawngtlai is Halkha Lai Lingua or Halkha language (Lahnim, 2015:3). The Lais are of Mongoloid stock in their origin and the language belongs to Tibeto-Burman branch of Sino-

Tibetan linguistic family (Hrekung, 2019:29). The Lais after setting in the hilly region of Central China moved upward to Tibet after which they migrated towards Tibet. From Tibet, they further pushed forward to Burma by passing along the watershed between Brahmaputra and Salween rivers from the valley Hukong (Hengmana, 1982:3). The Lai people reached the valley of Hukong in the tri-junction of international boundaries of Tibet, China and Burma in 400 A.D (Hrekung, 2019:29). After a series of migration, they finally set foot in Hakha, the present capital of Chin state in 1400 AD (Hrekung, K, 2019:29). The People who are now living in the administrative area of Lai Autonomous District Council had migrated from the Chin Hills in Burma between 1800-1900 AD (Lahnim, 2015:3). Since the Lai are the descendents of the Hakhas and the neighbouring areas, no wonder the current Lai language spoken within the area of Lai Autonomous District Council is of Hakha's origin. The Lai language is not only spoken in Lai Autonomous District Council of Lawngtlai, rather, it is a widely-spoken language even in the triangular terrain of Hakha, Lawngtlai and Cox's Bazar (Lahnim, 2015:10). It originated around 200 BC and has taken its concrete form around 750 A.D by the time that they lived on the bank of river Chindwin. It was first reduced into writing by Macnabb in 1891 and in 1899, the Lai alphabet was formed by Arthur and Laura Carson. Many researchers are of the opinion that the Lai language is the oldest language among Central Chin language (Zirliantluanga, 2015:14). Lai languages is rich in vocabulary, idioms and phrases. Several languages like Duhlian tawng (Mizo tawng) and Mara language had branched out from the Lai language. Even the present widely common language of Mizoram, that is Duhlian language depends to a large extent on Lai language till today in literature (Chhuanawma, 2005:27; Zirliantluanga, 2015:14).

Christianity, no doubt, made a significant contribution for the Lai language by reducing the Lai language into written forms and by translating several writings into the Lai language, however one cannot help but look back history of the church and Christianity in Mizoram. Welsh missionaries brought Christianity to Mizoram during colonial era from the geographical north which gradually spread towards the south. Meanwhile, on the other side of the international border, the first missionaries among the Lai people were an American couple who entered Hakha in 1899. Rev Larson and his wife gradually learnt and preached in Lai language among the Lai people in Chin Hills. Whereas in India, 'the Lai people were bombarded with the Lusei-preached Christianity from the north'. Soon the Lai people in India got comfortable with the Lusei sermons, prayers and also the Bible written in the same language (Hmingthanzuali, 2015:62). Mr. T. Hrangzuala, an influential religious leader has rightly said that, 'While Christianity had become an instrument to develop the Lushei and the Mara language a written form, the Lai language was left out. Moreover, education and gospel were imparted only through the Mara and Lushai Languages, therefore, the Lai language has slowly been drifted away. Christianity has brought education and development of literature in Mizoram which was a great blessing for all the people in Mizoram. However, it put the Lai people at a very critical situation that for the Lai, to become a Christian or to get education means to surrender their own identity, culture and language'. (Hrangzuala, 2000:43)

In this way, the Lai people have been slowly drifting away from their native language. In course of their series of migration and due to frequent contact with the Lusei Chiefs (Mizo Chief), the original Lai dialect has been deviated and become mixed up with Duhlian (Mizo) language. The Lai language has been alarmingly disappearing and the people residing in the 'Tuithlang area' (western side of Lawngtlai) no longer speaks the Lai language today. As such, the

Christian Missionary may be regarded as one of the reasons that made the Lai people alienated from their own native language.

TRADITIONAL FOLK DANCE

Just like all the tribals residing in the north east, so does dance occupies a central place in the Lai society. Dance was and still is occupying a major role in all the sad occasions like in the times of death, sickness and also in times of happy occasions like wedding, victory in war or raids and festive occasions and so on. A separate dance had been assigned for different occasions in the olden days. Therefore, the Lai folk dances always have a story to narrate which truly reveal the Lai vibrant and colourful culture. ‘Ruakkhatlak’ is one such dance that was usually performed by the village female youths on the occasion of ‘stillbirths’ on the hope that the departed soul would reach mithi-khua (paradise for the dead soul) safely and that he would not have a difficult journey. ‘Chawnglaizawn’ is another type of dance which was performed in times of death of village Chiefs and well-off persons of the village. The dance was usually performed by the most trusted servants near the dead body in order to swear his loyalty and faithfulness to the late chief or master and to serve him even in the next life cycle. ‘Sarlamkai’ is another type of dance associated with the celebration of war victory or raids. It is a war-like dance where the victor would bring back the head of the enemy to his village and would dance around the head of the enemy along with their weapons like swords, guns and so on. ‘Pawhlohnam’ is the most popular dance which was usually performed on festive occasions and in sacrificial ceremonies. It is a kind of dance performed both by male and female together standing alternately, making circles and holding one’s shoulder and waist. A drum and gong were also made use in this dance.

These original folk dances have slowly been losing their significance with the passage of time and this may be attributed to the work of Christian missionaries. The missionaries strongly condemned all these dances as the dances were usually associated with drinking alcohol (zu) saying that it is against the Christian culture. This led to the degeneration of the significances of the traditional dances which were inextricably linked with the traditional beliefs, customs and social values as they contradict with the Christian’s beliefs and ethics (Lalhminghlui and Robin, 2020:112). In this way, the unique and worth-treasuring folk dances have been partially losing their centrality due to the intervention of Christian missionaries.

LAI ANCIENT VILLAGE ADMINISTRATION

In ancient times, each village had a separate Chief which acted as the head of the state. The village administration was in the hand of the Chief and justice was dispensed by him along with the help of his ministers or villages elders (Upa). All the civil and criminal cases were tried and decided by the Chief. The cases were usually tried in the Chief’s house (Vanlalringa, 2012:11). The judgement made by the Chief and his Elders were final and unchallengeable. He is the supreme law. He appointed all important officials in his village and such officials are usually drawn from his relatives (Vanlalringa, 2012:11). The Chief while dispensing his justice must act and consult the customary laws and practices. However, note must be taken that the Chiefs were never autocratic but benevolent ruler (Chinzah, 2003:26). One of the most significant privileges of the Chief was the right to keep slave (Bawi/sal). There are five types of slaves (Bawi) which was prevalent in the Lai chieftainship (Vanlalringa, 2012:10); they were ‘Tlaihsal/ Khihsal’ (war captives), ‘Chhungkhungsal’ (a resaleable slave), ‘Rawlduhbawi’ (One who seeks refuge to the Chief due to sickness, poverty etc), ‘Rothensal’ (One who seeks

refuge due to fear of murder or revenge from the enemies) and ‘Tuangchhuaksal’ (Inherited slaves).

Prior to the British and the Christian Missionary’s intervention, the Lai Chief had fairly and justly dispensed his power and authority wherein his subjects were all living unitedly and harmoniously under his jurisdiction. However, with the British intervention in the Lai territory by the year 1889, the Lai Chiefs had been gradually losing their power. They even retaliated and fought back the British fearlessly which had led to the ambush and killing of Lt. Steward, leader of the survey party and two other British soldiers in February 3, 1888 (Reid,1976:16). One of the main reasons behind this attack was that the British unlawfully encroached upon their life-long territory not only once but several times (Lalthangliana,1989;105; Vanlalringa, 2012:9). In response to the killings, the British had eventually sent Brig.General Tregar to conduct the Chin-Lushai Expedition in 1889-1890. The main purpose of this Lushai expedition was to subdue and bring into justice the strongest Lai Chief (Hausata) who was held responsible for the murder of Lt. Steward (Chaterjee,1985:145; Vanlalringa.B,2012:9). By 1890, the British were successful in crushing all the Lai Chiefs and thus declared their sovereignty over the land of the Lai. The chieftainship was officially abolished in 1954. Before 1954, the British had intentionally retained chieftainship order for their own administrative convenience. In this way, the British merely recognised the Lai Chief as de facto rulers in their own lawfully land (Vanlalringa, 2012:14).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the once homogenous ethno-cultural identity of the Lai tribe has gradually eroded, as they have moved away from their traditional customary laws. The arrival of the British and Christian missionaries marked the decline of what was once a unified and contented society. Under the guise of development, the rich cultural heritage of the Lai people has partially vanished before their eyes, as their thought processes, values, and social norms have undergone profound changes. The once binding social values have lost their relevance, replaced by Christian norms and practices, leading to the ‘Christianization’ of the Lai culture. In light of these issues, this paper advocates for the intentional inclusion of cultural elements in all government development programs, ensuring that culture is given its rightful place in policy-making to achieve sustainable and balanced development for the Lai people.

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